

Supplementary material: Survey questionnaire

*Abbreviations are in parentheses

Q1. Please indicate your place of residence.

Rikuzentakata City (RES=1) / Other areas (RES=0)

Q2. Please indicate your gender.

Male (GND=1) / Female (GND=0) / Prefer not to answer (GND=NA)

Q3. Please indicate your age group.

Teens / 20s / 30s / 40s / 50s / 60s or older

Q4-1. Which areas should be prioritized for the improvement of Rikuzentakata's economy conditions? (Multiple answers allowed)

Agriculture (*ECO_agri*) / Fishery (*ECO_fish*) / Forestry (*ECO_forest*) / Tourism promotion (*ECO_tourism*) / Energy sector (*ECO_energy*) / Accommodation and restaurants (*ECO_accom*) / Transportation with outside areas (*ECO_transport*) / ICT utilization (*ECO_ICT*) / Job and business support (*ECO_jobs*) / Population increase (*ECO_population*) / None / Other

Q4-2. Which areas should be prioritized for the improvement of Rikuzentakata's living conditions? (Multiple answers allowed)

Medical services (*LIFE_medical*) / Welfare and elderly care (*LIFE_welfare*) / Childcare and education (*LIFE_childededu*) / Housing and vacant houses (*LIFE_housing*) / Local transportation (*LIFE_transport*) / Convenience of living (*LIFE_convenience*) / Disaster risk reduction (*LIFE_DRR*) / Community interaction (*LIFE_comm*) / None / Other

Q5. Do you think that economic revitalization is necessary for maintaining community interaction?

Disagree (*ECON_SOC=1*) / Neutral (*ECON_SOC=2*) / Agree (*ECON_SOC=3*)

Q6. How frequently do you communicate with or interact with your neighbors?

Very frequent (*SOC_local=5*) / Fairly frequent (*SOC_local=4*) / Neutral (*SOC_local=3*) / Rarely (*SOC_local=2*) / Never (*SOC_local=1*)

Q7. What elements do you think are necessary to increase community interaction in Rikuzentakata? (Choose up to three)

Events (*SOC_event*) / Traditional culture and history (*SOC_culture*) / Job and business opportunities (*SOC_jobs*) / Kindness and mutual help (*SOC_kindness*) / Respect for diversity (*SOC_diversity*) / Public relations (*SOC_PR*) / Public places to gather (*SOC_space*) / Neighborhood associations (*SOC_assoc*) / Childcare and elderly care support (*SOC_care*) / Inter-regional exchange (*SOC_exchange*) / None / Other

Q8. What do you think is important for promoting disaster risk reduction in rural areas? (Choose up to two)

Disaster awareness in ordinary times (*DRR_awareness*)

Disaster memory transmission (*DRR_memory*)

Disaster-prevention facilities (*DRR_facility*)

Disaster Information network (*DRR_network*)

Checking on others during disasters [not used in estimation]

Deployment of specialists [not used in estimation]

Support for volunteers [not used in estimation]

None / Other [not used in estimation]

Supplementary material: Policy package combinations

Alternative	A	M	F	N	Note
0000	0	0	0	0	Outside option (ASC)
1000	1	0	0	0	Awareness only
0100	0	1	0	0	Memory only
0010	0	0	1	0	Facility only
0001	0	0	0	1	Network only
1100	1	1	0	0	Awareness + Memory
1010	1	0	1	0	Awareness + Facility
1001	1	0	0	1	Awareness + Network
0110	0	1	1	0	Memory + Facility
0101	0	1	0	1	Memory + Network
0011	0	0	1	1	Facility + Network
1110	1	1	1	0	Awareness + Memory + Facility
1011	1	0	1	1	Awareness + Facility + Network
1101	1	1	0	1	Awareness + Memory + Network
0111	0	1	1	1	Memory + Facility + Network
1111	1	1	1	1	<i>Not included (never chosen)</i>

Note: A = *DRR_awareness*, M = *DRR_memory*, F = *DRR_facility*, N = *DRR_network*;

Supplementary material: Results of Hausman–McFadden tests

To verify the validity of the independence of irrelevant alternatives (IIA) assumption in the multinomial logit model, Hausman–McFadden Tests were conducted by sequentially removing each single-policy alternative (1000, 0100, 0010, 0001), while always retaining the outside option (0000).

Dropped alternative	Description	χ^2 statistic	df	p-value	Decision
1000	Remove alternative with A only	4.727	5	0.450	IIA not rejected
0100	Remove alternative with M only	9.128	5	0.104	IIA not rejected
0010	Remove alternative with F only	0.406	5	0.995	IIA not rejected
0001	Remove alternative with N only	0.117	5	0.999	IIA not rejected

Note: A = *DRR_awareness*, M = *DRR_memory*, F = *DRR_facility*, N = *DRR_network*.

In all four cases, the null hypothesis of IIA could not be rejected. Even when dropping 0100 (*M only*), the p-value was 0.104, which is above the 10% significance level. These results suggest that the IIA assumption is acceptable for the present model specification, and the estimates are not seriously biased by potential violations.